

Feedback on process modelling methodology

Diagrams - case study Pecorino Toscano

23-10-2023 Participants: P7, P8, P9, P10

24-10-2023 Participants: P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, P16

Process modelling methodology

1. **Diagrams:** a set of diagrams to represent the process transformation (case study)
2. **Procedure:** guidelines for living lab coordinators and a template for data collection (work in progress)

Aim of this meeting: **collect feedback on diagrams**

Expected duration: 60 minutes

This information will be useful to fine-tune the process modelling methodology to be adopted in CODECS

Socio-technical process modelling

Process model: a set of three types of diagrams

- **Structure** (*process to-be*) → system structure: actors, resources, activities, relations
- **Goal** (*process to-be*) → strategic dimension: actor's activities and relations in accomplishing the business goals
- **Business Process** (*process as-is and process to-be*) → process flow: actors' tasks, use of resources, communication exchange

Your feedback

For each diagram, 3 questions:

1. Is the diagram *complete*?
2. Is the diagram *understandable*?
3. Is the diagram *effective*?

Case study - Living Lab *Pecorino Toscano*

Starting point: Focal action situation (to be considered not final)

The Precision Sheep living lab, based in Manciano, Tuscany, is composed of a network of farmers (cooperative), a cheese making factory (pecorino), technical advisors (a veterinarian and an agronomist), the University of Pisa, CNR-ISTI, and a spin-off company in the agricultural sector. In the area, *milk production has been decreasing over the years because several farms have closed due to economic factors. It is increasingly critical for the factory to being able to estimate both milk quality and quantity in advance to better plan the production.*

In this line, the LL is testing digital solutions to: 1. support the advisors' work in the field, so to have more stable milk quantity and quality over the year; 2. provide information to the factory about the expected milk quantity and quality; 3. exchange practices and information among the farmers, and provide them with e.g. optimal feed composition to improve the milk quality; 4. providing farmers with information on their milk after analyses carried out in the factory.

The Living Lab is working on the introduction of a Farm Management Information System (FMIS) that integrates new and existing databases managed by different actors. The FMIS is composed of a mobile app and of a web-based dashboard for decision support. Additional functionalities are under development.

Structure diagram UML - plain version

Legend of UML symbols used

Structure diagram UML - expanded version

Legend of UML symbols used

Structure diagram

Completeness:

Comprehensibility:

Effectiveness:

Goal diagram - i*

Legend of symbols used

Goal diagram - i*

Legend of symbols used

Goal diagram

Completeness:

Comprehensibility:

Effectiveness:

Process diagrams - BPMN

process *as-is*: agronomist's process flow *before* the introduction of the digital technology

Legend of BPMN symbols used

Process diagrams - BPMN

process *to-be*: agronomist's process flow *after* the introduction of the digital technology

Legend of BPMN symbols used

Process diagrams - BPMN

process overlap

green + red → process before
 green + blue → process after

Legend of BPMN symbols used

Process diagrams - BPMN - example other pools process before

Process diagrams

Completeness:

Comprehensibility:

Effectiveness: